

REACTIVE POWER COMPENSATION IN SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAIC POWER STATIONS INTEGRATED INTO POWER SUPPLY SYSTEMS

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In centralized traditional power networks with a significant share of renewable energy sources, issues related to reactive power and voltage regulation begin to emerge. As a result, it becomes impossible to ensure adequate voltage stability in such systems without reactive power compensation devices. In networks integrated with renewable energy sources, reactive power compensation using static capacitor banks and synchronous compensators becomes critically important.

In Figure 1, the functional diagram of the reactive power compensation device in the integrated system is shown. A large portion of the missing power is reactive power, which is consumed through the transformer. This situation peaks at maximum power generation and maximum reactive power consumption by the solar photovoltaic station. It reaches its minimum value during minimal reactive power consumption or when the solar photovoltaic station is not generating energy. Since the power generated by the solar panel consists only of active power, the power factor is $\cos\varphi=1$. Depending on the type and characteristics of the consumers being supplied, the power factor values will range from $\cos\varphi=0.7$ to 1.0. A 630 kVA transformer has been integrated into the existing electric grid, and the installed capacity of the solar photovoltaic station is 29 kW[21-24].

Figure 1. Functional diagram of the reactive power compensation device in the combined system

When a solar photovoltaic (PV) station is integrated into the existing power supply system of industrial consumers, the amount of active power consumed from the grid decreases. This is because the majority of the active energy is produced by the solar PV station. The electricity generated by the solar PV station is consumed directly by the industrial electricity consumers at the same time. As a result, the active and reactive power consumed from the grid in the power supply system changes. When the supply from the solar PV station begins, the $\cos\varphi$ value decreases from the previous value where the solar PV station was not supplying energy. Therefore,

in order to reduce the energy losses caused by a low power factor ($\cos\phi$), special attention should be paid to adjusting the power factor ($\cos\phi$) to the desired value. A low power factor ($\cos\phi$) can reduce all the beneficial aspects of the solar PV station.

According to the analysis results, in integrated power supply systems, particularly in solar photovoltaic station-based power systems, the automatic and operational compensation of reactive power, as well as the ability to switch electrical equipment, is crucial. The development and implementation of contactless devices that are structurally simple, reliable, and cost-effective has been identified as one of the urgent tasks.